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Freud as Linguistic Innovator and Founder of Discourse

By

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In the preface to his authoritative biography of Freud, Peter Gay writes that Freud's presence is palpable—felt not only in Europe but even more so in America. His thinking, Gay asserts, is “woven into the very fabric of modern culture. (...) We all ‘speak’ Freud, whether correctly or not.” A few pages later, he reiterates: “It is a commonplace that today we all speak Freud, whether we are aware of it or not” (Gay 1989, pp. XIII and 3). The claim that ‘we all speak Freud’ invites reflection on its meaning and validity—an inquiry I aim to pursue here through a series of observations and associations. Perhaps the following story by Robert Gernhardt can help illustrate what it means to ‘speak Freud’.

“A man once came to Sigmund Freud and recounted a strange dream. In his dream, his Id had expressed instinctual demands, his Superego had attempted to suppress them, and his Ego had subsequently sublimated them. “Did you really dream that?” Freud asked. “Yes”, replied the man. Freud pondered for a moment and said, “The explanation of the dream is simple. Your Id is being suppressed by your Superego and is expressing instinctual demands, which your Ego...” “But that’s not an explanation—that’s my dream”, the man interrupted. “If you do not want me to interpret your dreams for you, you only have to say so”, Freud replied curtly and dismissed the man, who from that moment on suffered from a terrible inferiority complex” (Gernhardt 1998, p. 140f., transl. MK).

Admittedly, this is a somewhat eccentric example, but it may nonetheless be illustrative of our inquiry, as well as of the reciprocal influence of theory on its object, which we can observe here. After all, the man is dreaming on the theoretical level of metapsychology! Thus, he reminds us of the hero in the story ‘Dreaming as Waking’ from *Fantasies of a Realist* by Josef Popper-Lynkeus, as discussed by Freud—both men belong to that rare (or impossible?) species whose dreams require no distortion.¹

The Language of Psychoanalysis

But jokes aside, to speak Freud means, above all, to speak a language—his language. This is not to suggest that we would all master his brilliant style, but rather that individual terms coined by him—psychoanalytic terms—have entered everyday speech. Indeed, beyond the already mentioned ‘Id’, ‘Ego’, and ‘Super-ego’, words such as ‘Freudian slip’ (*Fehlleistung*), ‘libido’, ‘neurosis’, ‘Oedipus complex’, ‘projection’, ‘sublimation’, ‘trauma’, the ‘unconscious’, ‘primal scene’, ‘repression’, or ‘resistance’ have, to varying degrees, become part of common parlance when discussing psychological matters. They have, in any case, spread far beyond the specialized language of the discipline. Yet misunderstandings almost always lie in wait, as seen in the common reference, in German-speaking contexts, to the so-called *Freudsche Fehlleistung*—a term that tacitly, though falsely, implies the existence of other, non-Freudian *Fehlleistungen*.

The Dutch sociologist Abraham de Swaan has coined the term *proto-professionalization* for the phenomenon in which patients seeking professional therapy are usually not laypersons but individuals who, to some extent, have mastered psychological concepts and terminology—or at least know how to use them. Interestingly, this does not necessarily accelerate the therapeutic process, as psychotherapists can attest. Proto-professionalization is an aspect of the gen-

¹ Freud 1959-1973, Vol. 22, pp. 222-223 (= Freud 1960, Vol. XVI, p. 264).

eral psychologization of our culture, which now speaks of psychological problems where once it would have invoked demons, sins, bad humors, or fate (Cf. Brinkgreve et al. 1979, pp. 12f.). To be sure, Freud's depth psychology was not the sole driving force behind this development, but it became, one might say, emblematic of it, as Gernhardt's Freud anecdote has already made clear. However, it would be naive and premature to conclude from this that our society has fully embraced psychoanalysis. I think we all know from personal experience that the reception history of psychoanalysis—a history aptly described as the Hundred Years' War (Roudinesco 1982–1986)—is marked by persistent misunderstandings and malicious distortions. The general public's understanding of psychoanalysis, even among our contemporaries, can best be described as a caricature. Well, of course—how could it be otherwise? The dissemination—and thus the popularization—of any doctrine inevitably involves simplification. And, as we all know, resistance to analysis is inevitable, whether one experiences it as a narcissistic injury or not.

Even a caricature, however, is a form of representation. How, then, did Freud's terminology permeate everyday language despite natural resistance? Primarily, it seems, because Freud consciously sought to avoid the medical-psychiatric jargon of his time when forming his terminology, instead favoring ordinary German words such as *Abwehr* (defense), *Besetzung* (cathexis), *Familienroman* (family romance), *Krankheitsgewinn* (secondary gain), *Übertragung* (transference), *Widerstand* (resistance), and *Wiederholungszwang* (repetition compulsion). All of these are metaphors that acquire their precise, discipline-specific meanings only within the psychoanalytic context—that is, when they are analytically contextualized. It is precisely this rare ability in scientific writing that Hugo Ignotus had in mind when, as early as 1930, he lauded Freud's gift for “employing words and syntactic forms in their unexhausted, original meaning, thereby awakening them from the impotence of commonplaceness and imbuing them with new power” (Ignotus 1930, pp. 510ff.).

Fine examples of this include *Triebe* (drives)—“a word,” Freud noted, “that many

modern languages envy us for”²—or the simple word *Arbeit* (work), which he uses in new compounds such as *Trauerarbeit* (mourning work), *Traumarbeit* (dream work), or *Witzarbeit* (joke work): striking neologisms that replace lengthy explanations of the economic aspects of psychodynamics. The same applies to the unassuming word *Deckerinnerung* (literally, ‘cover memory’), which in fact conceals an *Ent-deckung* (‘un-covering’) with far-reaching consequences for memory research, as well as to Freud’s choice of the simple designations *Ich* (ego) and *Es* (id)—“mere pronouns instead of resounding Greek names,” as he explains, because in psychoanalysis, “we like to keep in contact with the popular mode of thinking and prefer to make its concepts scientifically serviceable rather than to reject them. There is no merit in this; we are obliged to take this line; for our theories must be understood by our patients, who are often very intelligent, but not always learned.”³ And, one might add, who grasp the nature of melancholy more readily, when Freud, in a formulation more poetic than scientific, explains that in this state of mind “the shadow of the object has fallen upon the ego”.⁴

It is regrettable that the translator and editor of the English Standard Edition—which continues to shape the world’s image of Freud more than the German *Gesammelte Werke*—James Strachey, overlooked this reference to popular ways of thinking. In his translation, *Besetzung* and *Fehlleistung* became ‘cathexis’ and ‘parapraxis’, while *Schaulust* and *Wisstrieb* were rendered as ‘scopophilia’ and ‘epistemophilic instinct’. Likewise, *Geisteswissenschaften* was translated as ‘mental sciences’ rather than ‘humanities’. While Freud avoided neologisms of Greek or Latin origin as much as possible, Strachey did not follow suit. To be fair, one must acknowledge that English, unlike German, inherently relies on Greek and Latin terms for body parts, diseases, and even, for example, the signs of the zodiac. Strachey’s lexical choices were therefore in keeping with the spirit of the English

² Freud 1959-1973, Vol. 20, p. 200 (= Freud 1960, Vol. XIV, p. 227).

³ Freud 1959-1973, Vol. 20, p. 195 (= Freud 1960, Vol. XIV, p. 222).

⁴ Freud 1959-1973, Vol. 14, p. 249 (= Freud 1960, Vol. X, p. 435); Freud 1959-1973, Vol. 18, p. 109 (= Freud 1960, Vol. XIII, p. 120).

language—though less so with the spirit of Freud’s own. In any case, Freud’s ‘democratic’ vocabulary—his deliberate avoidance of lexical *apartheid*, as Patrick Mahony phrased it (Mahony 1982, p. 53)—was not adequately preserved in the *Standard Edition*. On the contrary, the translation fostered a dogmatic and, at times, almost ‘depersonalized’ interpretation of psychoanalysis. Within the field, this contributed to the emergence of an unpalatable jargon in professional journals—the so-called ‘Psychoanalese’, which Theodor Reik once satirized in a parodistic scherzo:

“Fluent, if not always correct, Psychoanalese is spoken at the meetings and discussions of the psychoanalytic societies. Correct and sometimes elegant Psychoanalese may be read in the books and papers the members of the psychoanalytic groups publish. On all these occasions you will get the notion that here is a new language that tries to investigate unconscious processes by means of Greek and Latin terms. (...) It sweeps you off your feet, and you catch your breath (...) you will be kicked around like a football” (Reik 1948, p. 442).

How unfortunate that the transmission of Freud’s intellectual world abroad can almost be seen as an unconscious form of resistance against it! And what a mistake it is to assume that a dry scientification would enhance the persuasive power of his texts! It should be noted, by the way, that Freud—as his early, particularly his pre-psychoanalytic writings demonstrate—had a perfect command of medical terminology; a glance at the *Nachtragsband* of the *Gesammelte Werke* is enough to confirm this.

At the same time, the critique of Strachey’s translation of Freud, as put forward by Ornston (1982), Bettelheim (1983), Mahony (1989), and others, serves as a stylistic analysis *ex negativo*. For by portraying Freud’s language through its opposite, it highlights the very qualities that enabled its deliberate integration into popular modes of thought.

Because of my work on the indexes for the new Dutch edition of Freud’s writings (Freud 2006), I am currently rereading his entire corpus in chronological order—a fascinating experience, as it reveals how his ideas gradually take shape while

writing. One can observe his development over time: from a physician ‘treating’ his patients psychologically to an analyst who has learned to listen to them with evenly suspended attention; from a specialist in nervous disorders to the founder of a new psychological, anthropological, and cultural-analytical doctrine. His achievement is comparable to that of Marx in the social sciences or Darwin in biology. All three created a model of thought that enabled their successors to write Marxist, Darwinian, or psychoanalytic texts—to continue reflecting within the intellectual frameworks established by their masters, extending their lines of reasoning in their respective languages. Confident as he was, Freud himself compared the paradigm shift he introduced to those brought about by Copernicus and the founder of evolutionary theory. To put it pointedly, the linguistic innovator became, through his writing, the founder of an entirely new discourse on the psyche.⁵ His impact, presence, and relevance rest primarily on his texts, whether one interprets them accurately or not. The reason why reports of his ‘death’ are still greatly exaggerated is likely that he proved himself a master of the German language. Many today will agree with Kurt Eissler, who once wrote (in a letter to the author, January 8, 1969) that Freud’s writings “constitute a magnificent work of art”, and that only great works of art remain untouched by so-called progress.

Thinking Freud

The fact that psychoanalysis was, for a time, more popular in the Anglo-Saxon world (and, incidentally, in South America) than in Germany and its native Austria, despite its distinctly scientific English translation, reminds us that the psychoanalytic discourse is, though a linguistic practice, yet not merely a matter of carefully chosen words. To speak Freud must therefore mean more than just using certain expressions correctly or incorrectly; it also implies ‘thinking Freud’—or at least tending to think in the way he thought, even if only as a dwarf

⁵ Cf. Freud 1959-1973, Vol. 17, pp. 139-141 (= Freud 1960, Vol. XII, pp. 7-9).

on the shoulders of a giant. Demonstrating the imprint of psychoanalysis on everyday and scientific discourse is, however, no easy task, since it is often unconscious, unnoticed (as Peter Gay already observed), or deliberately denied, to the extent that only an expert can recognize Freud's traces within it. John Forrester compared this phenomenon to electric light, which we have become so accustomed to that we can hardly imagine the darker world of the past (Forrester 1997, p. 174). After all, who still thinks of Maxwell or Edison when flipping a light switch? Let us not forget Freud's pithy remark: "America is not named after Columbus."⁶ The English poet Auden hinted at what I mean in his 1939 elegy for Sigmund Freud with the much-quoted lines: "to us he is no more a person / now but a whole climate of opinion." To this climate of opinion, we owe a heightened readiness to take psychic reality seriously, a greater respect for psychological facts, and an increasing awareness that we are not motivated by demons, but rather by unconscious drives. The everyday discourse on our inner world, founded by Freud, contains—at least in its rudiments—the inkling that we are not masters in our own house. It testifies to the suspicion of our animalistic, instinct-driven, prehistoric-primitive, asocial-narcissistic primal nature and of the arduous cultural endeavor to come to terms with it.

Not long ago, an acquaintance told me that doctors had likely chosen their profession as a way to cope with their fear of illness. When I responded that this assumption of unconscious motives for a counter-phobic reaction formation was a typically psychoanalytic thought, he indignantly dismissed it. Freud, he claimed, was hopelessly passé. Such everyday encounters teach us that, while Freud laid the foundations for the modern discourse on the psyche, most participants in that discourse are either unaware of this fact or actively deny it. Just as Molière's Monsieur Jourdain was astonished to discover that he had been speaking prose all of his life without realizing it, we could assure many a contemporary that they 'speak Freud' without knowing or even wanting to. Even

⁶ Freud 1959-1973, Vol. 15, p. 257 (= Freud 1960, Vol. XI, p. 264).

many critics of psychoanalysis fail to recognize just how deeply Freud's thinking has left its mark on their own arguments.

As stated, Freud as a founder of discourse is inconceivable without Freud the linguistic innovator. Let us therefore now turn our attention to his linguistic talent. The fact that he was awarded the Goethe Prize in 1930 and that the prize for scientific prose, conferred annually since 1964 by the German Academy for Language and Literature, bears his name—the Sigmund Freud Prize—attests to the widespread recognition of his stylistic mastery. His linguistic gift at times manifested itself in pure creative play, as evidenced by the light, fluid style of such texts as the novella-like *Katharina case* in *Studies on Hysteria*, certain lectures, his interpretation of *Gradiva*, and his elegant essays *Screen Memories* and *On Transience*.

The topic of Freud as a writer has been frequently examined since Walter Muschg's seminal 1930 essay, to the point that it has become a recurring theme in Freud scholarship. In this essay, I will therefore focus only on one particular aspect that scholars such as Patrick Mahony (1987, 1989), Klaus Thonack (1997), and others have highlighted. In 1968, in accordance with Freud's own self-perception, I distinguished between the scientist—"who subordinated all his literary abilities to the presentation and communication of his science"⁷—and the writer. Mahony and others, however, reject this dichotomy, arguing that Freud's view was a self-misunderstanding: his linguistic talent was not merely a vehicle for his thought, but its instrument (Meisel 1981, p. 3). In other words, Freud's writing process did not merely represent his thinking—it constituted it (Thonack 1997, p. 20). Indeed, the unconscious, they contend, was not first discovered by Freud and then formulated in language; rather, it articulated itself through his writings.

⁷ Lütkehaus 1990, p. 12. Freud famously resisted being praised as a writer, as he saw it as a form of resistance to his teachings.

Pensée pensante

Closely related to this is the fact that Freud's thinking often appears *in actu*. In this method of *pensée pensante*, thinking and writing blur into each other, as primary and secondary processes celebrate their mystical marriage. Especially in the texts Freud himself distinguished as 'genetic' rather than 'dogmatic' presentations, we do not read the product of his thought but witness the process itself. We do not see the completed fabric but look into the loom, "where a single tread stirs a thousand threads" (Goethe, *Faust I*, line 1924). We partake in reflection as it emerges, watching the creative thinker at work in the phase of *inventio*. Notably, Mahony repeatedly emphasizes this 'processiveness' (or 'ongoingness') in Freud's discourse, suggesting that this associative mode of thinking requires the reader, in turn, to adopt a state of evenly suspended attention in their reading. This insight is highly original and warrants further exploration. Mahony speculates that Charcot's improvisational *Leçons du mardi* (Tuesday Lectures) at the Salpêtrière, which Freud translated, served as a model. But one might also think of Lessing's writings, which Freud himself named as his stylistic model (cf. Jens 1991 and 1992). It is likely that this processiveness helped establish and disseminate the specifically psychoanalytic discourse. Unfortunately, such things cannot be proven, but that is in the nature of the matter.

Numerous self-reports indicate that Freud consciously employed this ability to remain open to the unconscious while writing. His discovery and mastery of free association—a completely novel mode of discourse—must have greatly influenced this practice.⁸ He wrote to Fliess that, at the beginning of a paragraph, he often did not know where it would lead; his work was "entirely written following the unconscious, according to the famous principle of Itzig the Sunday Rider: Itzig, where are you riding? How would I know, ask the horse."⁹ This is a significant

⁸ Cf. Freud 1959-1973, Vol. 19, pp. 261-265: 'A Note on the Prehistory of the Technique of Analysis' (= Freud 1960, Vol. XII, pp. 307-312: 'Zur Vorgeschichte der analytischen Technik').

⁹ Freud 1986, p. 348f., letter dated July 7, 1898.

metaphor, which he later (in *The Ego and the Id*) uses to illustrate his structural model of the psyche: “Often a rider, if he is not to be parted from his horse, is obliged to guide it where it wants to go; so in the same way the ego is in the habit of transforming the id’s will into action as if it were its own.”¹⁰ Regarding *Civilization and Its Discontents*, he told Sterba: “One does not compose such works; they compose themselves” (Sterba 1985, p. 116)—in this case, I would add, by working through one beloved quotation after another. In an interview, he confessed: “When I sit down to work, and take my pen in hand, I am always curious about what will come forth, and that drives me irresistibly to work” (Knoepfmacher 1979, p. 447). In the *Introductory Lectures*, he noted: “There is often something in the material itself which takes charge of one and diverts one from one’s first intentions. Even such a trivial achievement as the arrangement of a familiar piece of material is not entirely subject to an author’s own choice; it takes what line it likes and all one can do is to ask one self after the event why it has happened in this way and no other.”¹¹ He echoes this sentiment in *Moses and Monotheism*: “the work proceeds as it can, and often presents itself to the author as something independent or even alien.”¹² Cromwell’s dictum, “A man never mounts so high as when he does not know where he is going,” was one of his favorite quotes, Sachs informs us (Sachs 1945, p. 67).

This synergy of primary and secondary processes in writing certainly explains the stimulating, “thought-provoking” quality of much of Freud’s work. The ‘open’ conclusions of his essays, which always end quite abruptly, appear to suggest: This is not my final word on the matter; it is a stimulus for further thought. Or, in his own words: “I do not wish to arouse conviction; I wish to stimulate thought (...). You should listen and allow what I tell you to work on you.”¹³

Mahony never tires of expressing his admiration for Freud’s prose, precisely

¹⁰ Freud 1959-1973, Vol. 19, p. 25 (= Freud 1960, Vol. XIII, p. 253).

¹¹ Freud 1959-1973, Vol. 15, p. 379 (= Freud 1960, Vol. XI, p. 393).

¹² Freud 1959-1973, Vol. 23, p. 104 (= Freud 1960, Vol. XVI, p. 211).

¹³ Freud 1959-1973, Vol. 16, p. 244 (= Freud 1960, Vol. XI, p. 250).

because it combined “exposition and enactment” of the unconscious (Mahony 1987, p. 149). In an aphoristic summary, he characterizes Freud’s style as similar to a joke and Lacan’s style, by contrast, as dream-like (Mahony 1989, p. 91). In terms of the role of the unconscious in each discourse, I take this to mean that Lacan allowed more space for the unconscious. The question remains, however, where the optimal balance lies between consciousness and the unconscious, and between primary and secondary processes, in scientific language. Jokes *must* be understood; they are speech acts, communicative acts. Dreams, on the other hand, *can* be interpreted, but they are not intended as messages.

Klaus Thonack argues that it was only Mallarmé (whom Freud did not know) who, in his literary oeuvre, found the solution to the problem of representing the unconscious (Thonack 1997, p. 95). However, I would like to note that, regardless of how permeable and indistinct the boundary between poetry and psychoanalysis may be, and despite the validity of the observation that they are sibling disciplines, does not their sibling rivalry also possess its own justification?

Freud’s linguistic style, let us not forget, encompasses various modes of expression. It is easy to distinguish the systematic Freud of the *Three Essays* from the empathetic psychologist of the case histories, the pessimistic cultural analyst from the political leader of a movement. The academic psychology handbooks, which, entirely in the spirit of the *Standard Edition* and its medicalizing tendency, perceive but the dogmatist and system-builder Freud, overlook the intuitive clinician, the imaginative anthropologist and the speculative philosopher (cf. Richards 1989). And yet, it is precisely these aspects that bear witness to his originality and creativity and have remained influential to this day. In a letter to Jung, Freud once wrote with rare clarity: “I am not at all organized for inductive research, being wholly oriented toward intuition, and I imposed extraordinary discipline upon myself when I undertook the establishment of a purely empirical psychoanalysis”¹⁴—one of the very few instances in which he saw through his own

¹⁴ Freud & Jung 1974, p. 523, letter dated December 17, 1911.

scientific self-misconception (as Habermas calls it).

One might add to Mahony's thesis of 'processiveness' that every written text, including scientific texts, is to some extent guided by primary process thinking, while still maintaining that their quality ultimately depends on the intellectual rigor of the author—on the coherence of his secondary process, on the success of secondary elaboration. And before the reader wonders whether the advice to loosen the reins while writing, following the example of Itzig the Sunday rider, might finally be the *via regia* to winning the Sigmund Freud Prize for scientific prose, let me remind them that a purposeless ride, though it may lead to new discoveries, can just as easily end in hopeless confusion. If the Sunday *rider* were to become a Sunday *hunter*, he might, as the saying goes, easily miss his mark. This brings us to the venerable question of genius, before which my horse now balks. Let us not mount a high horse, but rather recall that original Sunday rider of whom Cervantes tells us in the second chapter of his novel: "Don Quixote continued on his way, which was none other than the one his horse wanted, for he believed that this was the essence of adventures" (cited after Flem 2003, p. 177)—and, I would add, of intellectual adventure as well.¹⁵

¹⁵ An earlier version of this article was published twice in German, under the title 'Freud als Sprachschöpfer und Diskursbegründer'. It first appeared in Wolfram Mauser and Joachim Pfeiffer, eds., *Freuds Aktualität* (Freiburger literaturpsychologische Gespräche 26), Würzburg, 2007, pp. 245–254. That same year, it was republished in Wolfgang Hegener, Eike Hinze, Halina Katz-Eringa, Regine Locket, and Ullrich Motz, eds., *Erinnern und Entdecken: Zur Aktualität Sigmund Freuds*, Gießen, 2007, pp. 27–38. The present English translation is by Maria Kardaun.

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